

STADIEM

STARTUP DRIVEN INNOVATION IN EUROPEAN MEDIA

D1.1 COMMUNITY BUILDING STRATEGY

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Abstract	<p>Deliverable 1.1 is the first output of Task 1.1 Community Building Strategy and Community Management. It is the result of a participatory process that included a workshop with the STADIEM project partners and entails the basic principles and strategies on how the STADIEM consortium aims to construct and engage its community.</p> <p>The document provides an overview of the matrix that was used to gather the necessary information, as well as an exhaustive overview of the results.</p> <p>Building on the exercise, the consortium subdivided the stakeholders into three groups based on the level of engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform: audiences that need to be informed, but that will not play an active role - Convince: audiences that need to be informed and convinced of the project's ambitions, in such a way that they are able to contribute - Engage: audiences that play an important role in the progress and sustainability of the project <p>For each of these groups, the exercise defined existing initiatives and possible opportunities to accommodate them.</p>
Keywords	Community building strategy, community management, community engagement

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
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CO	Confidential to STADIEM project and Commission Services	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

PROCESS

The Community Building Strategy document is the result of a participatory process that included a workshop with all STADIEM project partners, organized by the project coordinator, VRT.

The participatory process followed different phases:

1. Prioritizing the different activities that relate to the STADIEM community
2. Mapping different groups of stakeholders based on their level of engagement:
 - a. Inform: stakeholders that should be informed
 - b. Convince: stakeholders that should be convinced
 - c. Engage: stakeholders that should be engaged
3. Determining the contributions of closely involved partners and outlining existing initiatives from the different project partners to address stakeholders

RESULTS

We have defined a set of community building tools per group of stakeholders, taking into consideration the distinction between inform, convince and engage. We then translated the community building tools into a set of KPIs we wish to meet.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 GOAL

This deliverable is the first output of Task 1.1. Elaborating on the community building methodology, it contains the basic principles and strategies on how the STADIEM consortium wants to construct and engage its community.

1.2 APPROACH (WORKSHOP & LIVING DOCUMENT)

To define these principles and the strategies, VRT organized an online workshop together with all project partners. Facilitated via the online collaboration platform Miro, the workshop focused on prioritizing project goals that relate to our different stakeholders and leveraging existing input and initiatives to develop a community around the project's ambitions. The workshop lasted 2 hours, after which the project partners were able to make further additions. This document describes the processed input.

As a starting point, the partners filled in an information grid with on the one hand the project's objectives, and on the other hand the relevant sectors. Subsequently, the consortium mapped the existing initiatives and possible opportunities to accommodate the stakeholders. See appendix A for the results of the workshop. The most relevant findings are discussed in the current deliverable.

2. STRATEGY

2.1 OBJECTIVES LINKED TO ORGANIZATION & STAKEHOLDERS

The first part of the workshop was to connect the different objectives of the project to the related stakeholders. A first version of this was published in the grant agreement. In the workshop, we further worked on exploring and defining additional links and stakeholders (and their sub-groups).

For this, three project ambitions and related subtasks were discussed:

- Facilitate a start-up to corporate to market tech transfer
- Build a sustainable network
- Create an acceleration framework

The second part of this exercise lied in prioritizing the different subtasks. Each participant of the workshop received 3 votes per category. As such, an indication could be given for the level of engagement that is required from each stakeholder. A table with objectives and related stakeholders is shown in appendix A. The number of votes is shown in the second column.

Figure 1 visualizes the end result of this exercise.¹

¹ We are aware the resolution of the visuals is not ideal. It is an unfortunate consequence of turning Mirko into .jpeg into .wordx. The images in high resolution are at the EC's disposal if need be.

FIGURE 1: LIST OBJECTIVES AND RELATED STAKEHOLDERS

2.2 APPROACH (LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT)

As indicated in 2.1, we started outlining our community building strategy based on the level of engagement needed from our different stakeholders. To determine this distinction between the different groups of stakeholders, the participants were asked to subdivide them in 3 different categories. Based on the involvement that is needed to advance on our project objectives, we listed the categories as follows:

1. **Inform** – This first group of stakeholders needs to be informed and updated about the project and its outcomes. The level of engagement is limited to raising awareness and sharing information, which will be addressed via our communication strategy.
2. **Convince** - The second group of stakeholders is the group we aim to convince. These are stakeholders that need to be persuaded about the value of the project, as we count on their timely contributions.
3. **Engage** - The third group are the stakeholders we want to strongly involve. These are considered to be the (future) active members of our community and are expected to actively participate in the community. In addition to directly contributing to the project, stakeholders engaged in the project can also act as ambassadors. As such, they are able to leverage their own networks and amplify the impact of the STADIEM project.

Figure 2 visualizes the outcome of that exercise and Table 1 gives an overview of the levels of engagement per group of stakeholders.

FIGURE 2: MAPPING OF LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT OF THE DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDERS

TABLE 1: MAPPING OF LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT OF THE DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDERS

	Inform	Convince	Engage
Cultural / artistic actors			
Non-media sectors / Verticals			
Standardisation bodies / initiatives			
Media producers Traditional media Operators			
Technologists / tech innovators			
Incubators / accelerators and Investors / corporates			
Users / audience civil society			
SMEs and start-ups (in media tech domain) -> related sectors			
Researchers in Industry and Academy			
Public authorities Regulators Policy makers			
Education (schools / academia...)			

2.3 INFORM

2.3.1 Stakeholders

Inform - The first group of stakeholders is the one that will be informed as we want them to be familiar with STADIEM, but we do not expect them to play an active role in the project. The following 7 stakeholder groups need to be informed about the project and are addressed via our communication strategy and planning.

- Cultural / artistic actors
- Non-media sectors / verticals who are not related to the media industry (the non-media sectors and verticals who are related to the media industry are discussed in the category convince)
- Standardisation bodies / initiatives
- Users / audience / Civil Society
- Public authorities / Regulators / Policy makers

2.3.2 Initiatives

To inform this particular group of stakeholders about STADIEM, we will deploy:

- Our STADIEM website
- The STADIEM promotional video on YouTube
- Communication campaigns on social media, such as LinkedIn and Twitter
- Word-to-mouth campaigns during industry/networking events

2.4 CONVINCING

2.4.1 Stakeholders

Convince - The second group of stakeholders is the group we aim to convince. We want to keep them more informed than the first group as they are more likely to follow the project, albeit from a distance. We defined 3 different stakeholder groups in this category.

- Non-media sectors / Verticals who are related, for example because they use crossroad technology
- Media producers, Traditional media, Operators
- Researchers in Industry and Academy / Education (Schools)

2.4.2 Initiatives

The next step in the workshop was to define the different initiatives for stakeholders that we need to convince. In developing our community building strategy for these groups, we considered the following questions:

- Are there subgroups that need to be defined?
- What benefits does this audience bring to the community?
- What are they looking for? (needs / wants)
- What do we want these stakeholders to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)
 - Beneficiaries: who are the primary recipients of the community activities?
 - Drivers: who are the people leading the community activities?
 - Ambassadors: who are the advocates that you can tap to support the community activities?
 - Funders: who are the people who can help fund, sustain or support the community activities? (based on the stakeholders in the change process, Community Builder published by Ghost²)
- How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives and potential opportunities)

² Miikka Leinonen & Lana Kristine Jelenjev, *Community Builder. Designing Communities for Change* <Community Strategy – GhostCompany.fi> (last consulted on 19/03/2021).

FIGURE 4: MEDIA PRODUCERS / TRADITIONAL MEDIA / OPERATORS

FIGURE 5: RESEARCHERS IN INDUSTRY AND ACADEMY / EDUCATION

TABLE 2: CONVINCCE

	Non-media sectors Verticals (related; automotive, education) → crossroad technology	Media producers Traditional media Operators	Researchers in Industry and Academy / Education (Schools)
Subgroups	Culture	Media producers: written, video, social, audio, broadcasters, distributors	Groups involving innovators/research projects
	Government	Traditional media: radio, broadcast, newspapers / magazines	
	ICT & Tech (aka Cloud providers)	Operators, System integrators, developers, tech stack providers, 3rd party providers	
	EduTech		
	AD / Martech		
	Mobility (media)		
What benefits does this audience bring to the community?	In-depth tech insights, architecture (ICT, tech)	Potential deal flow, testing, mentors, introductions, investors, inspiration, pivoting, experts	Bigger reach in the specific environment
	Connection with content, audience (culture)		Access to innovators
	Connects with whole society, bridging a potential chasm (government)		Experimental R&D environment /
	Possibility to use or pilot infrastructure		Expertise
	Solve a targeted problem, address a tender		
	Provide a pilot case		
	Provide additional funding or support = through partnerships with other (govt) programs		
	Provide access to corporates and big clients		

What are they looking for? (needs / wants)	Fresh ideas	Ideas to solve problems, pilots, knowledge transfer, innovation process, learnings, community	Reaching other innovators (expanding contacts)
	Peer-to-peer exchange		Perspective/aims/focus areas
	New (general) technology		
	Cultural sector à innovation what they do not know how to manage		
	New clients / partners		
	Use cases		
	Adtech/Martech (new solutions for their clients)		
	Broadcast-quality UI/UX / insights		
	Access to the masses, access to comms technology		
What do we want these audiences to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)	Culture = beneficiary	Experts, introduction, networking, feedback, inspiration, knowledge transfer, testing and piloting	Spread the word
	Government = funder	Drivers?	Funders / ambassadors
	ICT/tech = driver		
How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives + potential opportunities)			
VRT	Methodology & insights	Future Media Hubs network	Network: project partners
	Partnership opportunities in proposals	Link with EBU community	
	Ecosystem	Links to local schools in Flanders (Belgium)	
Media City Bergen	Cross-mapping in the ecosystems. Innovation projects cross-industries	Potential clients, mentors, experts, testing and piloting, profiling, become part of an ecosystem	Innovation projects including own ecosystem and academia

	PropTech/Fintech, Bergen kommune, UIB, museums. Trafikkflyt/transport/elb il		
NMA	Consultancy relationships with national and federal German governments and institutions	Existing ecosystem of NMA	City University New York, European Academia (e.g. several German Universities, Fraunhofer Society)
		Investors and partners of NMA	
Storytek	Access to edutech	Existing Ecosystem of Storytek & EA	Media innovation & research academia in the Baltic / North- Eastern European Region
	Access to various EU and governmental programs	Investors and Media sector partners of Storytek & EA specifically in Baltics, US and Asia	
	Access to corporates and largescale innovation leadership networks aka Kellog Innovation Network / TWIN	Media Systems Integrators	
	Access to VC funds and M&A sector Access to start-up growth and scaling and expert networks, i.e. Scalewise, Sales Impact Academy, Salto	Public Broadcasters in the Media innovation & research academia in the Baltic / North- Eastern European Region Festivals, markets and trade shows in the media / audiovisual industry including Cannes Marche Du Film, Berlinale, Rotterdam, Tallinn, Geneva, Bucheon etc.	
EBU		EBU members community	
Martel	Communication assets (visual/copy/social media and website updates)	Communication assets (visual/copy/social media and website updates)	Communication assets (visual/copy/social media and website updates)

	Targeting/sharing among our contact within several non-strictly media and research and innovation groups and projects we've worked on (5GPPP, NGI, FED4FIRE) which have connection to media/next generation internet	Targeting a database of Swiss contacts, which include broadcasting/media organisation and services	Targeting/sharing among our contacts within several research and innovation groups and projects we've worked on (5GPPP, NGI, FED4FIRE) which have connection to the academic/education field
	Keeping relevant partner organisations and projects informed		Keeping relevant partner organisations and projects informed
	Targeting national contacts related to ICT and Future and Emerging Technologies		
F6S	F6S network of start-ups and innovators	F6S community	Network: technical experts
	Partner Organisations	Scouting start-ups	Access to technical and industry experts
	Media Projects		

2.5 ENGAGE

2.5.1 Stakeholders

Engage - The third group are the stakeholders we aim to strongly involve. We expect them to participate actively in the community and we also want them to take an ambassadorial role. We defined 3 different stakeholder groups in this category.

- Technologists / tech innovators
- Incubators and accelerators Investors / corporates
- SME's and start-ups (in media tech domain) -> related sectors

2.5.2 Initiatives

The next step in the workshop was to define the different initiatives for the stakeholders categorized as convince or engage. The following questions were considered in engaging these audiences:

- Are there subgroups that need to be defined?
- What benefits does this audience bring to the community?
- What are they looking for? (needs / wants)
- What do we want these audiences to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)
 - beneficiaries: who are the primary recipients of the community activities?
 - drivers: who are the people leading the community activities?
 - ambassadors: who are the advocates that you can tap to support the community activities?
 - funders: who are the people who can help fund, sustain or support the community activities?

(based on the stakeholders in the change process, community builder published by Ghost³)
- How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives and potential opportunities)
 - Because not every partner was represented in every breakout session, they were able to check and complete this information after the workshop was finished.

³ Miikka Leinonen & Lana Kristine Jelenjev, *Community Builder. Designing Communities for Change* <Community Strategy – GhostCompany.fi> (last consulted on 19/03/2021).

FIGURE 6: INCUBATORS / ACCELERATORS AND INVESTORS / CORPORATES

FIGURE 7: SMES AND START-UPS

TABLE 3: ENGAGE (TECHNOLOGISTS / TECH INNOVATORS)

Technologists / tech innovators	
Subgroups	No specific subgroup identified for this category.
What benefits does this audience bring to the community?	This audience is invited to propose new technical solutions to emerging needs in the media sector, in terms of production, distribution, and re-use of media content.
What are they looking for? (needs / wants)	Looking for coaching, competent feedback from peers on their envisaged innovative solutions/products, funding for development and for go-to market activities.
What do we want these audiences to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)	Exchange ideas, co-develop, identify business models for market adoption.
How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives + potential opportunities)	
VRT	Methodology and insights
	Partnership opportunities in proposals
	Ecosystem
	Sandbox
	Future Media Hubs network
Media City Bergen	Experts, SoMe-ambassadors, presenters/lecturer
NMA	Access to radical / disruptive media innovation, accelerate product development and strategy
Storytek	Showcasing innovation through Storytek / EA partnerships with major innovation events/festivals, platforms
	Opportunities to catalyze innovation to large scale project with Storytek / EA partnerships with moonshots programmes and networks, i.e. Twin, Accelerate Estonia
	Tie in tech innovations with policy through Storytek's activities in policy shaping regionally and in the EU.
EBU	Co-design of solutions, co-development of tool, Proof of Concept / testing / deployment of innovative technology
	Guidance on standardization and promotion among EBU member organizations.
Martel	Communication assets (visual/copy/social media and website updates)
	Targeting/sharing among our contacts within several research and innovation groups and projects we've worked on (5GPPP, NGI, FED4FIRE) which have connection to media/next generation internet but also other fields (automotive, ICT in general)
F6S	Leveraging on existing involvement of F6S in other research and innovation projects and EU initiatives targeting technology development and transfer.

TABLE 4: ENGAGE (INCUBATORS AND ACCELERATORS)

Incubators and accelerators - Investors / corporates	
Subgroups	Corporate accelerators/incubators
	VCS
	Business Angels
What benefits does this audience bring to the community?	VC – Dealflow
	VC – Financing
	VC – Clear attraction for start-ups
	VC – Opportunities for portfolio start-ups to grow or achieve further investments
	Corporates – Piloting opportunities
	Corporates – Visibility and PR
	Corporates – Co-financing
	Corporates – Clear attraction for start-ups
	Accelerators – Dealflow
	Accelerators – Access to their markets
	Accelerators – Access to experts
What are they looking for? (needs / wants)	VC – Opportunities to scale their start-ups
	VC – Co-financers
	Corporates – New technologies
	Corporates – Visibility
	Corporates – Way to be better than their competitors
	Corporates – New business cases
	Corporates – Be important in innovation
	Corporates – Corporate sustainability
	Accelerators – Money
	Accelerators – Partnerships
	Accelerators – Ways for their portfolio start-ups to grow
What do we want these audiences to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)	Beneficiaries
	Ambassadors in the best-case scenario
How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives + potential opportunities)	
VRT	Network
	Methodology and insights
Media City Bergen	Network
	Ecosystem
NMA	Network
	Easy testing

	Cases
	Partners and investors
Storytek	Wide VC and investors network globally
	Access to selected top-tier corporates in the EU, Asia and the US
	Access to scaling and growth expertise networks
EBU	Providing insights on added value of innovative technologies / products for the sector and areas of potential applications
Martel	Communication assets (visual / copy / social media and website updates)
	Targeting a database of Swiss contacts, which include start-ups and SMEs
F6S	F6S network

TABLE 5: ENGAGE (SME'S AND START-UPS IN RELATED SECTORS)

Incubators and accelerators - Investors / corporates	
Subgroups	Alumni portfolio of start-ups
	Related project databases
	F6S database
	Crunchbase
What benefits does this audience bring to the community?	Experience
	Innovation
	Buzzwords and trends
	Knowhow / expertise within their field
	Cultural change
What are they looking for? (needs / wants)	Money
	Connections
	Mentorship / Scaling
	Cooperation
	Opportunities
	Corporates – New business cases
	Corporates – Be important in innovation
	Corporates – Corporate sustainability
	Accelerators – Money
	Accelerators – Partnerships
Accelerators – Ways for their portfolio start-ups to grow	
What do we want these audiences to do? (beneficiaries / drivers / ambassadors / funders)	Beneficiaries
	Ambassadors
How can your organization help facilitate this? (map existing initiatives + potential opportunities)	
VRT	VRT Sandbox
	Sandbox Hub
Media City Bergen	Incubator
	Network
	Events both physical and digital
NMA	Whitepapers (corporates and start-ups)
	Newsletter
	CRM (clique.AI)
	Events: Live Launch & Spotlight, Media Match (Dealroom)
Storytek	Partnership deals with industry leading expertise networks
	Relevant regional VC networks

	Tailored access (meetings, curated events, etc.) to premium vertical clients or focused search by vertical clients
EBU	Visibility at EBU events on relevant topics
	Cross-collaboration and participation in future projects/initiatives by EBU and / or its members
Martel	Communication assets (visual / copy / social media and website updates)
	Targeting a database of Swiss contacts, which include start-ups and SMEs
F6S	Database
	Targeted scouting campaign
	Related projects in other domains (cross-collaboration)

2.6 COMMUNITY BUILDING TOOLS

The community building tools follow the 3 different categories we've defined in terms of the level of engagement of groups of stakeholders: we develop a set of tools for the stakeholders we aim to inform, a set for the stakeholders we want to convince, and one for the stakeholders we pursue to engage.

TABLE 6: COMMUNITY BUILDING TOOLS

Level of engagement	Community building tools
Inform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STADIEM website • STADIEM promotional videos • Communication on social media, such as LinkedIn and Twitter • Word-to-mouth campaigns during industry/networking events
Convince	<p>In addition to the tools we use to inform, the community building tools to convince are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitations to participate in workshops/events • Engage at workshops/events • Targeted publications
Engage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars to promote the programme • Showcasing and getting together at international/events, facilitated by the STADIEM network, for example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SXSW ○ Slush ○ The Big Score ○ IBC ○ NAB • Showcasing and getting together at international/events, organised by the STADIEM network, for example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ VRT: Media Fast Forward, MME Inspiration Days ○ MCB: Tech Conference, Future Week ○ Storytek: Latitude59, Start-up Day, Industry @ Tallinn & Baltic Event, Cannes Marche Du Film ○ NMA: MediaMatch, MediaMatch New York, NMA Demodays ○ Martel: NGI4ALL, NGIoT, Orchestra Cities ○ EBU: Broadthinking, EBU Metadata Developer Network, EBU/ASBU Week of Technology, EBU Creative Forum • The Big Bang event that will proceed the match-making phase (WP4) • Participation in at least 4 project-related events • Demo Day at the end of the project • Access to and integration in the partners' hubs and networks • Videos, interviews and success stories online, for example on the website • During the match phase, we will explore whether or not the engaged community would require a dedicated STADIEM community forum throughout and after the project duration.

2.7 IMPACT ASSESSMENT

The impact assessment of the community building tools for the inform and convince stakeholders largely corresponds with the communication plan set out for the STADIEM project (WP 5 and D 5.2). For the engage stakeholders, we will explore the need and impact of the proposed tools during the match phase after the first batch of start-ups has been selected.

TABLE 7: IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNITY BUILDING TOOLS

Level of Engagement	Tools	KPIs
Inform	STADIEM website	> 1.500 unique visitors per month
	STADIEM promotional videos	4 videos per year 100 views per video
	Communication on social media	Twitter > 300 followers LinkedIn > 100 followers
Convince	KPIs inform	See above
	Workshops / events	At least 6 per year
Engage	KPIs inform + convince	See above
	Webinars	2 per open call
	We will explore the need and impact of the proposed tools during the match phase after the first batch of start-ups has been selected, in order to deploy community building tools dedicated to the needs of the start-ups involved in the programme.	

3. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The Community Building Strategy is the result of a participatory process that was kicked off by a workshop on consortium level organized by VRT. All partners showed a high level of commitment towards the workshop and thus towards maximizing the potential of the STADIEM.

During the workshops, the partners were asked to prioritize the different activities related to the STADIEM community, to map the different group of stakeholders and to outline existing community building initiatives per partner. The result is the subdivision of the stakeholders into three groups (inform / convince / engage) and a corresponding set of community building tools.

For the inform and convince stakeholders, the community building tools largely correspond with the communication plan that is developed in full detail in WP 5 / D 5.2. For the engage stakeholders, we will use the match phase to investigate what tools would be the most useful in order to get and keep the stakeholders engaged. We will most likely do so under the form of a workshop with the project partners as well as a survey with the start-ups that were selected for the first match phase of the STADIEM programme.

